

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS, MEANS, AND METHODS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF STATE POLICY IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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The development of tourism, especially in the modern unstable economic situation, shows that the tourist complex is not the same in the regions, which leads to different approaches to the development of the state support model and the regulation of the economic mechanism.

The effectiveness of tourism is an important factor that stabilizes the socio-political situation in the regions where there are recreational and cultural facilities and creates the basis for the sustainable development of tourism in the regions.

At the same time, the imperfection of the management system and state support can hurt tourism.

The main goal of improving tourism is to create a modern and competitive tourist complex based on the use of unique tourist and recreational resources, domestic traditions, scientific achievements of research in the field of tourism, and providing solutions to the main tasks¹:

- meeting the needs of citizens of the local, CIS, and foreign countries, creating conditions for high-quality tourist services and recreation of the population;
- increase the contribution of the tourist complex in the development of the regional economy;
- preservation and rational use of natural resources and spas, scientific, cultural, and historical heritage.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to develop several basic principles to achieve the stated goals:

¹ Сурков С.Г. Международный туризм в России: проблемы развития и управления / С.Г. Сурков, В.И. Криворучко. – М.: Советский спорт, 2009. – 214 с.

- conducting a complete inventory of objects in the field of private tourism, developing and implementing a system of registration of these objects, and forming a register of private tourist objects;
- for successful operation of all types of touristic organizations of organizational and legal forms and types of ownership, improvement of the regulatory and legal framework for the development of tourism;
- formation of reasonable tax policy and economic mechanisms to stimulate the development of tourist organizations in the regions;
- attraction of investments in tourism with state guarantees and other measures of local support;
- preservation, rational use, and protection of natural resources and recreation areas;
- creating conditions and opportunities for the cooperation of tourism organizations with transport, agriculture, industry, banking and investment structures, insurance companies, and advertising agencies to form a high-tech and competitive domestic market of tourist services;
- strengthening state support and regulation of the industry through the international system of service certification;
- implementation of a uniform personnel policy through the system of training, retraining, upgrading, and certification of leaders and specialists in the field of tourism.

Forms of state regulation of the tourism sector provide the main direction of influencing the sustainable development of the sector to achieve a dynamic balance between supply and demand for tourist products and services. In the conditions of the transformation of the economy, all methods and means of regulation of the tourism sector should be interrelated. Their complex use allows them to effectively solve the issues that arise before the participants of relations in the tourism industry.

Regulation of tourism is a synthesis of state and market mechanisms of both direct and indirect regulation. The tourism regulation system includes a set of general and special, short-term and long-term measures, methods, principles, and tools based on a specific concept. In this case, in our opinion, it is necessary to form a balance between the market and state mechanisms of influencing the development of the tourism market.

Currently, the main goal of the effective development of the tourist services market is to create a favorable competitive environment that ensures the development of this market by improving economic relations in the field, and is aimed at solving the following tasks:

1. Achieving a market balance between supply and demand in the market of tourist services;
2. Improving the levers of organization and regulation of mutual socio-economic relations between its subjects in the market of tourist services;
3. Development and implementation of the strategic concept of the development of the tourism sector based on the formation of a competitive environment in the market of tourist services.

Table 1.2
Classification of tourism regulation methods²

Classification marks	A group of tourism regulation methods
According to the level of exposure	International, national, regional, and company-wide measures.
According to regulatory measures	Legal, administrative, economic, organizational, social, and informational.
According to the method of exposure	Direct (legislative basis of regulation, administrative measures) and indirect (economic measures).
According to the description of measures	General (the concept of tourism development in the Republic of Uzbekistan) and special (regional tourism development programs)
According to the object of influence	Construction of new accommodation facilities, tourist infrastructure facilities, catering facilities, transport-logistics structures, entertainment industry, cultural and sports facilities, tourist exhibition facilities, etc.
According to funding sources	A combination of the state budget, foreign investors' funds, private sector funds, and public-private partnerships.
According to the directions of influence	Measures affecting the supply and demand of tourist goods and services, comprehensive measures to reduce the impact of seasonal factors by diversifying tourist products and services.
According to the nature of exposure	Encouraging, limiting, prohibiting, protective measures.
According to the exposure period	Long-term, medium-term, short-term measures.

² Developed by the author.

A general classification of state regulation of tourism is presented in Table 1.2.

The mentioned methods of regulation ensure the balance of supply and demand for tourist products and achieve various results of planning the parameters of the tourism market in the conditions of stable development of the industry in response to changes in the socio-economic situation.

The implementation of tourism development tasks requires the development of practical proposals based on a scientific approach to the content of state regulation of tourism.

Tourism as a social sector of the economy can be described as the influence of state bodies on the activities of economic entities and market conditions to provide conditions for the functioning of market mechanisms.³ The process of state regulation is a complex task, which includes the development of economic policy, the justification of its rules, and the choice of means and methods of implementing this policy.

State regulation of tourism by the object of influence means measures to regulate three interrelated parts, namely: tourist resources, development of tourists and financial flows in this area.

The content of the regulation of tourism by the state is determined by the goals of the state bodies, as well as the tools available to the state tourism agencies in the region in conducting economic policy.⁴ In a market economy, these consist of:

- providing information to participants of the tourism market about the general state of the country's economy and this sector, its development prospects;
- justification of the most important points of the economic policy expected to be implemented in the field of tourism by state bodies at this stage of the development of the country's economy;

³ Рыночные механизмы управления санаторно-курортной сферой / Л.В. Криворучко, В.И. Криворучко. – М: Финансы и статистика, 2003. – 176 с.

⁴ Дымченко, А.С. Маркетинг и логистика в системе государственного управления санаторно-курортной сферой / А.С. Дымченко, Л.В. Криворучко, А.П. Скрыпкин. – Сочи: Из-во СГУТиКД, 2000. – 112 с.

- implementing measures for the development of the state sector of the tourist complex as one of the important means of state influence on economic processes in the country.

Reference

1. Рыночные механизмы управления санаторно-курортной сферой / Л.В. Криворучко, В.И. Криворучко. – М: Финансы и статистика, 2003. – 176 с.
2. Дымченко, А.С. Маркетинг и логистика в системе государственного управления санаторно-курортной сферой / А.С. Дымченко, Л.В. Криворучко, А.П. Скрыпкин. – Сочи: Из-во СГУТиКД, 2000. – 112 с.